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Challenges Faced by United Nations Peacekeeping Missions in the Democratic Republic of Congo and the Way Forward

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ABSTRACT

Over the years, a plethora of problems bedeviling the African continent attracted academic interest with many inquiries on the causes and possible solutions. Countries such as the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), since independence, have experienced ceaseless spectre of instability leading to the presence of the United Nations peacekeeping mission for several years till present. The DRC, just like any other African country, is confronted by several issues which have contributed to the numerous threats to the country's peace and security over the years. Today, the country hosts one of the most significant, longest, and most expensive UN peacekeeping operations. Using the case of DRC, the research analyses the role UN peacekeeping operations play in maintaining peace and stability in DRC using qualitative analysis. The study aims to uncover the actions taken by the African states and regional organizations towards assisting DRC to attain relative stability. The study observes that many factors impede the UN peacekeeping operations from achieving their tasked mandate in DRC. Therefore, the challenges and future prospects of the UN peacekeeping missions in DRC are also thoroughly examined. Almost invariably, in the international intellectual discourse, contemporary challenges in DRC and the African continent are attributed to colonial legacy, lack of good governance compounded by weak institutions and corrupt leadership, scramble for the continent's natural resources, and external interference mention but the most common.

Keywords

Africa, Challenges, Democratic Republic of Congo, Peacekeeping missions ,Prospects , United Nations

Introduction

Over the last few decades, United Nations peacekeeping operations deployed numerous peacekeeping operations to maintain peace and security in the African continent. However, the instability in Africa still prevails despite the multiple peacekeeping missions and their immense efforts. Africa faces many inevitable hurdles with deep-rooted problems dating back to its history. For the past twenty years, the succeeding UN Secretaries-General have been singing the praises of UN peacekeeping as an indispensable tool for

maintaining international peace and security, securing justice and human rights, and promoting sustainable development.¹ However, UN peacekeeping operations play a vital role in restoring stability in Africa. They face various challenges and issues that require rigid and more effective peacekeeping operations.

The challenges faced by the peacekeeping missions, particularly the missions in Africa, include lack of knowledge on country-specific political and cultural situations, inhospitable environment, upholding its impartiality, making decisions on when to use force. Furthermore, peacekeeping operations are trying to maintain peace when there is no peace to keep, lack of funding and the inability to tackle the root cause of African conflicts. Other factors include non-effective mandates, ineffective enforcement of arms embargo, non-tackling of the root cause of conflict, and non-participation of troops from developed nations.² Finding troops with robust organizational training, equipment, and logistical support to effectively undertake the complex and often dangerous tasks required of UN peacekeepers remains a crucial determinant of an operation's success. However, this is easier said than done since the member states who possess such troops have often proven unwilling or unable to make them available for UN peacekeeping operations.³ The countries willing to send troops are from developing countries without adequately trained human resources and logistics. UN peacekeeping is very difficult because it slows down troop deployment to countries in crisis. The study argues that UN peacekeeping operations should have standby troops who are always ready for deployment instead of waiting for troop-contributing countries in times of crisis. Unfortunately, the UN peacekeeping operations cannot have their army because of impartiality, but the UNSC permanent members will have control, power, and influence over the military.

Every day, the UN peacekeepers protect millions of civilians in conflict situations, supporting fragile political processes to find lasting solutions and building sustainable peace. However, as the study argued earlier, UN peacekeeping has become difficult because of many political, humanitarian, and military issues.⁴ However, unintended consequences of these peacekeeping operations affect the success rate and the legitimacy of these missions. Several other factors that impede the efforts of UN peacekeeping missions, especially in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), are discussed, and arguments are made on whether these missions are still a viable tool for the maintenance of peace and stability in the DRC. The study also examines the actions taken by regional organizations and neighbouring countries in trying to assist DRC in achieving relative

stability after many years of chaos. Several factors determine the success of the peacekeeping missions, and they will be examined and discussed. The failures of the peacekeeping missions will be highlighted and examined as to why they are failing in DRC despite their duration in the country. Furthermore, the prospects of the peacekeeping missions in DRC are also discussed.

The figure below shows a bar graph indicating the responses to a questionnaire conducted by the author to find out the challenges faced by the UN peacekeeping operations in Africa. According to the data collected, 26% of the participants think it is a lack of knowledge on different political and cultural situations. In comparison, 22% think that inadequate manpower and logistics as the biggest hurdles for UN peacekeeping. Other challenges listed were unintended consequences by 15% of the respondents, inhospitable environment by 14% of the respondents, inadequate media coverage by 14%, and, lastly, non-participation of troops from developed countries by 9%. The author used this questionnaire to support its findings regarding the challenges faced by peacekeeping missions in Africa.

Figure 1.1 Challenges faced by UN peacekeeping in Africa

Source: Based on the survey conducted by the author

1.1 Factors that impede peacekeeping missions in DRC

Although the UN has several mechanisms, resolutions, and resources aimed to enhance its peacekeeping operations success, there are still setbacks and issues challenging the aiming of peacekeeping operations successfully.⁴ The DRC has proved to be the state where the challenges and complexities of African internal conflicts are the most defiant to UN peacekeeping.⁵ Many challenges impede the success of these missions and vary according to individual countries but, the focus will be on missions in DRC. The first challenge for

UN peacekeeping missions in DRC was after their first deployment with the ONUC mission when the Congolese government gave their full consent to establish the mission but later withdrew it. The lack of cooperation in the international arena is perceived as one of the challenges encountered by peacekeeping operations.

This is also true for DRC. The lack of cooperation by the Congolese government became a challenge for the ONUC mission because host state consent is widely held as a critical success factor for peace operations as part of the peacekeeping principles. The Congolese government is one of the most decisive factors contributing to the failure of the peacekeeping missions in the country because of its complex geopolitics that failed its state institution. The study will elaborate why it argues that the failure of the state institution in DRC is a challenge for the peacekeeping operations. The Congolese state failure is internal, mainly political. It remains a crucial challenge for achieving more excellent stability by the MONUSCO in the DRC.⁵ Due to the collapse of the state institution in Congo, it has a very weak army which hinders its partnership with the UN mission to get rid of rebel groups in the country. The issue of host consent was a doorway to many more cases that impeded the success of the UN peacekeeping operations in DRC. It will be further elaborated in the study. The issue of host consent reduced the number of deployments for the MONUC mission. Alongside the difficulty of finding a balance between the consent of host states and the doctrine of impartiality, the evolution of the use of force also contradicts the central pillars of peacekeeping.⁶

The Security Council established a robust peacekeeping operation in DRC called MONUSCO, which went against their principle of impartiality. Although the expanding robustness of peacekeeping operations affects the peacekeepers' ability to remain impartial, it is the promotion by the UN of this more extensive use of force that has the most significant impact on its credibility, as peacekeepers suffer from political and structural limitations that diminish their ability to conduct their missions successfully.⁷ The study argues that the DRC is partly responsible for the lack of success of the UN peacekeeping missions in the country. However, the Security Council also plays a role in the failures of these missions because the mediation efforts in DRC have neglected the politics of the region, and the study argues that the lack of country-specific knowledge on the different political and cultural situations hinders the peacekeeping operations' mandate to become a success in the DRC. Many of the environments in which UN peacekeeping was recently deployed lacked a clear political framework to guide the government and other parties to the conflict towards an inclusive, non-violent post-conflict political order.⁸

As a result, the mandates given to peacekeepers in Africa are not compatible with civil war situations and affect their reputation as impartial forces. In the case of the Democratic Republic of the Congo, this problem stems from a misconception of the situation.⁸ The study sees the need for the UN peacekeeping operations to continue working closely with other regional organizations in Africa such as the African Union, SADC, and ECOWAS, just to name but a few, as they have better knowledge of the root causes of instability in affected countries. The joint Hybrid missions prove to be halting limited success in restoring relative stability in most countries they operate in, for instance, the case of UNAMID in Darfur. The support of neighbouring countries is also encouraged. However, in the case of DRC, neighbouring countries like Rwanda and Uganda have proved to have different interests in the country, and their presence in the DRC has only worsened the stability. In addition, their activities in Congo also obstruct the efforts of the peacekeeping operations to restore peace.

On the other hand, neighbouring states have engaged in pervasive backing of rebel groups and are involved in the war economy directly or through proxies.⁸ Different motives and interests are highlighted as some of the factors that hinder the efforts of peacekeeping missions in the country, and the study argues that UN peacekeeping missions have different motives and interests in the country; hence, they keep expanding and extending their mandate. The DRC is a mineral-rich country with many actors interested in exploiting them. The longer the UN peacekeeping missions stay in the country without any results of relative stability, it raises a concern of whether they have other motives of exploiting the country by aiding troop-contributing countries to exploit the countries riches using the missions as a disguise. The act of sexual abuse by peacekeepers is another issue of great concern as they take advantage of the vulnerable women and children in DRC. The study argues that the UN peacekeeping operations should find a way to rid the DRC of these foreign actors and build a vital state institution because the failure of governance is a common source of violent conflict.

In general, multidimensional UN peace operations have successfully prevented the resumption of war. Yet, they have not succeeded in establishing compelling and legitimate institutions of governance: peacekeeping works, but state building fails.⁸ The study suggests that UN peacekeeping operations can uncover the real reasons why Rwanda has interests in DRC. This would be a doorway to restoring the territorial integrity of DRC. Poor organization by UN peacekeeping mission concerning the unclear mandate, issue of impartiality, and lack of resources are some factors that affect the success of the tasks in DRC. Furthermore, the DRC has few passable roads, little infrastructure, and poor or no social services to its people.⁹ This makes it difficult for the UN peacekeeping missions to carry out their tasked mandate.

Inhospitable environments

UN peacekeeping operations are deployed in harsh environmental conditions that are remote and treacherous with minimal resources and substantial logistical challenges. The numbers of peacekeepers on the ground may be declining, but mandates' expectations and difficulty are continuously multiplying. The environment for peacekeeping is no longer benevolent; nonetheless, peacekeepers continue to operate in an atmosphere of armed conflict with poorly defined borders or cease-fire lines with no assurance for their safety regardless of their mandate.

The role of UN peacekeeping has been broadened as they no longer just observe, monitor, or retain cease-fire support. However, current peacekeeping operations are tasked with executing multidimensional and sensitive tasks, such as combating sexual and gender-based violence, reforming security sectors, and building the rule of law. With time peacekeepers are slowly but surely becoming peacebuilders. UN peacekeeping missions operate in the most dangerous and challenging environments globally, dealing with conflicts or their aftermath that others cannot or will not address. We can achieve what others can't, but success is never guaranteed.¹⁰ In DRC, the MONUSCO mission operates under a highly volatile region with significant levels of ongoing violent conflict, which puts their safety at risk. Attacks have been carried out on security forces and MONUSCO, including an attack in December 2017 in which 15 Tanzanian peacekeepers lost their lives and 44 others were wounded.¹¹ Operations deployed in remote areas with harsh physical terrain and a lack of access to infrastructure face substantial logistical problems.¹² The DRC has extremely poor infrastructure, which hinders the peacekeeping missions when it comes to accessing very remote areas in need of intervention by limiting road movement. Even military vehicles have difficulty moving within the DRC because the rugged geography makes the territory impassable.¹³

Non-participation of troops from developed countries

The UN peacekeeping operations are faced with a challenge of lack of support from developed countries when it comes to deploying troops for peacekeeping operations. Peacekeeping operations require skilled manpower that is well trained and highly equipped to facilitate their operations to provide international peace and

security. The majority of the countries contributing troops to peacekeeping operations are developing countries such as Rwanda, Nigeria, Pakistan, India, just to name a few. These countries are not technically advanced in military training required for peacekeeping operations. These peacekeepers from developing countries need to be well trained before being deployed to be helpful and practical on the ground. In the case of the DRC, a shortage of highly trained and well-equipped peacekeepers has exacerbated insufficient troop numbers and an imprecise mandate. The Congolese state has a very weak national army named FARDC. The military is poorly paid, inadequately equipped, and needs extensive reform.¹³ In addition, there is an issue of misconduct of peacekeepers from the troop-contributing countries, such as sexual abuse of women and children in the DRC. Although in 1999 the UN's Security Council authorized peacekeeping forces in the DRC and established the United Nations Organization Mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo (MONUC) to help bring peace and stability to the conflict-ridden country, shortly after MONUC was established, reports regarding sexual exploitation and abuse by UN peacekeepers emerged.¹⁴ The study argues that the Security Council should do a background check on the behaviour and conduct of personnel being taken to be a part of the peacekeeping operations. This would help avoid any unintended consequences that may hinder the mission's progress.

Developed countries are part of the UN organization and are even permanent members of the Security Council. Still, their support for the deployment of troops is hardly noticeable even though they have well-trained and advanced military and technology to deal with the ongoing threats to peace and stability in Africa. Of the five permanent members of the UN, China is now the biggest provider of peacekeepers to UN missions, and other 'emerging' powers from the Global South are becoming actively engaged in the normative and operational debates over UN peace operations, while different forms of South-South cooperation are replacing or supplementing conventional donor-dominated 'partnerships'.¹⁴ Non-participation by UNSC permanent members in UN peacekeeping operations is a significant hindrance to peacekeeping missions in Africa as the ongoing instability in Africa requires a lot of manpower. Still, developed countries only choose to contribute more to the peacekeeping budget. Therefore, the developed countries should continue to be encouraged to prove their highly skilled and equipped manpower towards the missions. It would be very beneficial for the success of the missions.

Lack of cooperation in the international arena

The bureaucratic principle of UN peacekeeping is one of the reasons why it's facing some challenges. UN peacekeeping operations have to seek permission or an invitation from the nation experiencing or is involved in conflicts. This is a hindrance because not all governments cooperate with UN peacekeepers or even hand

them permission to start their operations. In cases like these, even if permission is granted by the governments involved in conflicts, it does not guarantee that they will work together or cooperate with the UN peacekeeper, thus failing numerous operations. The Security Council deployed peacekeeping missions to the DRC at the request of the Congolese government. However, the Congolese government had different expectations of how the ONUC mission assisted them. The issue of consent became a problem on the side of the Congolese government when their expectations of the forceful removal of Belgian troops and other foreign actors from the DRC. None of the rebel groups were favourable to the UN presence in the DRC, and Belgium had given its consent to ONUC but not to withdraw its forces unconditionally.¹⁵ As a result, the Congolese government became hostile towards ONUC and launched government-led military and political attacks towards the mission.

The lack of cooperation from the Congolese government indicated that they had withdrawn their consent for the operation of ONUC in DRC. With no consent and numerous member states wanting to redefine the mandate of ONUC by the end of 1961, the deficient legal justification made the Secretary-General obliged to bring ONUC to a rapid exit.¹⁶ The Congolese government still hasn't changed towards other missions such as MONUSCO, which is still having difficulties restoring relative stability in the country. Many interlocutors observed that, for many years, MONUSCO has been working with a government that does not want it to be there and that has asked several times for its departure. However, it maintained its legal consent for MONUSCO's presence.¹⁷ The lack of cooperation from DRC hinders the success of the operation.

Inadequate manpower and logistics

Another challenge the UN peacekeeping operations face is an insufficient provision of the necessary resources vital to carry out peacekeeping operations. The conflicts in Africa are very complex and require adequate resources such as well-trained personnel, skilled manpower, and essential equipment. Some peacekeeping operations fail due to inadequate manpower and logistics and tarnish the name of the UN peacekeepers because it seems as if they are failing to meet their time frame for operations and not adhering to their mandate. In terms of logistics, the peacekeeping missions deal with robust operational mandates, effective enforcement of arms embargo, acquiring troops from developed nations, and adequate funding and logistics.¹⁷

The lack of all these resources leaves a lot of African countries in great suffering because UN peacekeeping cannot do much to bring conflicts under control, which is very frustrating for UN peacekeepers. Thousands

of African peacekeepers are trained in basic military skills such as military policing, infantry tactics, human rights awareness, and engineering. The African peacekeeping forces would respond quickly to crises to provide humanitarian or peace support operations by improving their military skills.¹⁸ This would reduce the need to ask developed countries to contribute more troops towards the peacekeeping missions as the troops from developed countries would be as equally trained since they are the ones who contribute more troops towards the missions. Another limitation arises from "the lack of training and guidance for peacekeeping troops rotating in and out of the mission, the limited will and ability of certain contingents to use force," and "leadership and command and control issues at all levels."¹⁸ However, MONUSCO is not achieving relative stability in DRC because of the lack of the relevant resources and the poor infrastructures and roads of the country it operates in. The military component of MONUSCO continues to face the operational and tactical challenges of not having adequate means and capacities to fulfil the mission, having contingents unwilling to execute the given mandate, and having poor leadership and pre or in mission training.¹⁸

The figure below shows a bar graph indicating the responses to a questionnaire conducted by the author to find out why the efforts of the UN peacekeeping operations in maintaining peace and stability in DRC are proving to be ineffective. According to the data, 35% of the participants responded that different motives and interests besides restoring peace and stability in DRC. In comparison, 22% of the participants think that lack of skills and country-specific knowledge hinders the efforts of the peacekeeping operations. Others listed efforts impeding the efforts of peacekeeping operations were poor organization by the UN peacekeeping missions by 20% of the respondents, the insufficient number of personnel by 12 % of the participants and lastly, lack of resources by 11%. The study used this questionnaire to support its findings regarding the efforts of the UN peacekeeping operations in the DRC missions.

Figure 1.2 Factors impeding the efforts of UN peacekeeping operations in DRC

Source: Based on the survey conducted by the Author

1.2 The Role of Regional Co-operation in Building Peace.

The threats to peace and stability in the DRC have become of great concern to the African continent because if the situation is not contained, it will spill over to other African states. Nine countries border the DRC: Angola, Burundi, Rwanda, Uganda, Republic of the Congo, Central African Republic (CAR), South Sudan, Tanzania, and Zambia. Thus, the DRC conflict, particularly its intractability, has numerous risks for neighbouring countries and the region due to the negative consequences of unstable conflict spillovers.¹⁹ However, some of the DRC's neighbouring countries, like Rwanda and Uganda, contribute highly towards the levels of instability in the country and impede the successful efforts of the UN peacekeeping missions. However, due to the complexity of the nature and root causes of instability in the DRC, the regional organizations have to be involved in the UN peacekeeping efforts towards restoring stability in the DRC or any other troubled African state. They have a better understanding and knowledge of the history of events that might have led to the causes of violent situations. The Regional Organizations (RO) are not only inherently endowed with cultural sensitivity and local knowledge of their region, but these factors provide them with a better ability to utilize early warning systems.²⁰ Therefore, the partnership and cooperation between the regional organizations and the UN peacekeeping mission will increase the chances of tackling and sharing the burden of insecurity in Congo. The March 1999 UN Report also acknowledges some of the advantages of using regional organizations in resolving disputes, such as their better knowledge about the root causes of a

conflict and parties and personalities involved in the conflict.²⁰ Due to the complex nature of current wars, the UN is increasingly utilizing regional and sub-regional governmental groupings in Africa for peacekeeping.²¹

The African Union is one of the organizations that used its efforts to intervene in devastated African states before deploying the peacekeeping missions. The AU is working vigorously to strengthen its capacity and partnership with the UN to contribute to its most crucial function: maintaining international peace and security.²² For example, the AU contributed 4000 troops to Darfur while the Security Council was trying to determine if the violence in Darfur was extreme. The current era has witnessed the increasing need for involvement by the African Union (AU) and subregional

organizations to be more involved as first responders to conflict situations in the region.²³ Its efforts led to establishing a solid partnership with the UN peacekeeping operations. However, the joint hybrid operations have shown to be achieving limited success, which indicates that it is necessary to have partnerships that will benefit political cooperation with regional and sub-regional organizations in supporting the UN peacekeeping operations. The AU is not the only regional organization that works with the UN peace operations. Still, other regional organizations such as SADC and ECOWAS have also shown support towards the peace missions in the region. Indeed, while the DRC reflects the diversity of conflict intervention actors, ranging from the UN and AU to other RECs and bilateral initiatives, SADC has increasingly recognized that it is not an alone player in the DRC.²³ On February 24, 2013, eleven African heads of state and four representatives of leading international organizations met in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, to sign a new commitment to security, stability, and peace in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC).²⁴ This shows the determination and dedication of these regional organizations' efforts to improve the security situation in Congo.

1.3 The way forward for UN peacekeeping missions in DRC

However, the UN peacekeeping missions also face significant challenges: political volatility as the electoral process unfolds; ongoing rebel violence in the east of the country; expanded responsibilities without resources to match; inadequate political will from the DRC government to improve security and governance in the country; and fatigue from the international community, which has supported a UN peacekeeping presence in the DRC for over 16 years and has not seen the results that it hoped to achieve.²⁴ The presence of UN

peacekeeping operations in DRC and Africa has made a tremendous impact towards establishing relative stability in war-torn regions with violent situations. As long as there are threats to peace and security in the area, the Security Council will continue to deploy peacekeeping missions in the African continent. However, several factors have to be considered regarding the prospects of the UN peacekeeping missions in Africa, particularly in MONUSCO. The prevalence of threats to peace and security in DRC amid the presence of MONUSCO indicates that the mission's lack of understanding and knowledge of the political and cultural situation in the country has not been tackled accordingly. The DRC's geopolitics situation is complex; therefore, if this root cause of instability is not addressed, it will be hard for MONUSCO to restore stability in the country. The way forward is that MONUSCO should put more effort towards understanding the geopolitics and root causes of instability. This would allow the mission to develop a comprehensive and integrated approach towards building a solid-state institution in DRC. A vital state institution in DRC would lift the burden from MONUSCO because the Congolese government's territorial integrity would be restored, and there would not be any interference in the country's political matters by regional actors such as Rwanda and Uganda. The UN peace missions would focus on restoring stability in DRC instead of fighting rebel groups from neighbouring countries pushing their agenda. If the UN peace missions can find a way to drive these foreign actors (Rwanda and Uganda) from DRC, it will be a step towards establishing a solid-state institution without interference. In the future, the UN peacekeeping missions should continue to work closely with regional or sub-regional organizations that have a better understanding of the genesis of the political and cultural situation of DRC.

Furthermore, the joint hybrid missions achieve limited success in restoring relative instability in some African states like Darfur. It is duly noted that the joint hybrid peace mission in Darfur was not as complex as it is with the case of DRC because the UN mission worked together with the African Union peace mission to bring relative stability to the country. Although eventually, the mission was withdrawn despite ongoing violence, some peacekeepers remained behind to monitor the situation.

The study believes the MONUSCO mission can benefit highly from the partnership between the UN peacekeeping missions and other regional organizations going forward. This approach will strengthen coherence between political, military, humanitarian, and development-related activities of UN peacekeeping operations in the future.²⁴ The Security Council should establish a clear and coherent framework and mandate for its missions upon deployment and ensure that they are fully prepared in logistics and manpower. For instance, the peacekeeping mission in DRC is a true example of a peacekeeping mission that has dragged on for years. It is the most expensive UN mission because the mandate of the UNSC upon being deployed to the country was never to focus on rebuilding its state institution but instead focused on fighting the rebel groups. The UNSC should do a thorough check of the behavioural conduct of peacekeepers before deploying them to unstable countries to avoid them from taking advantage of the vulnerable population and engaging in activities

that would tarnish the image of the UN peacekeeping operations. Many foreign actors are interested in these resources, especially in DRC with enormous natural resource wealth and geostrategic location.

Rwanda's failed UN peacekeeping operations resulted in a genocide that led to many refugees fleeing into the DRC. The immigration of refugees acted as a catalyst to the current instability in the DRC. If part of the mandate for the UN peace missions involved the support of countries to deny sanctuary to fleeing hostile forces, the DRC would not have faced so many challenges regarding its instability. Going forward, the study concluded that the UNSC, through its mandates for the peacekeeping missions, should encourage countries to avoid hosting immigrants fleeing hostile forces to prevent spillover of the violent situations across borders. At the same time, they do their best to control the violent situation where the immigrants were fleeing from. The Congolese government should also be more cooperative with the peacekeeping missions deployed in their country to make the peace process easier for the peacekeepers. The success of UN peacekeeping, in particular, depends on the readiness of the parties involved to commit to peace and to make the political compromises inherent to any peace process.²⁵ The country is rich in minerals and natural resources with abundant fertile lands. Any saner efforts of UN peacekeeping operations level to introduce land reforms, ensure youth training, provision of specialized machinery, and interest-free loans will make this war-torn country prosper. DRC alone can feed the whole African region if the land is made cultivable, which is not a big deal. Therefore, the UNSC collective might shun outside interference aimed at treacherous exploitation of resources by any state.

Conclusion

The Democratic Republic of Congo has been battling threats to peace and stability before acquiring its independence from Belgian rule. The instability in the DRC attracted several UN peacekeeping missions over the years, but the quest for restoring stability continues. The missions deployed to the DRC have encountered several challenges such as operating in inhospitable environments, lack of cooperation from the Congolese government (issue of the consent), non-participation of troops from developed countries, inadequate manpower, and logistics and lack of knowledge on the political and cultural situation in DRC. The study highlighted the actions taken by African states and organizations towards assisting the Congolese government and UN peacekeeping mission in restoring relative stability in DRC. However, Rwanda and Uganda are an exception because they contribute to the instability in the country. Regional organizations such as AU, SADC, and ECOWAS are endowed with knowledge of the political and culture of their region. Hence, the study noted that their cooperation and partnership with UN peacekeeping operations could help to unravel the complexity

²⁵ Swigert JW. Challenges of peacekeeping in Africa. Remarks of the Principal Deputy Assistant Secretary of the Bureau of International Organization Affairs, Department of State, to the Committee on International Relations, US House of Representatives, October. 2004 Aug;8.

of the situation in DRC. The study deduced that the joint hybrid missions should be deployed more because they have achieved limited and relative success in UNAMID, Darfur.

The problems faced by DRC are very complex; having poor political and governmental leadership made matters worse and challenging for the UN peacekeeping operations to maintain peace and security in the country. The study outlined that lack of solid leadership, failure of state institutions, inequality and marginalization, natural resource exploitation, violence, and conflicts are the challenges faced by DRC. Corruption in the economic and political sphere, state collapse, natural resource wealth, ethnic strife, and foreign actors' involvement in political affairs are listed as the causes of instability in DRC. The study highlighted that inhospitable environments, non-participation of troops from developed countries, lack of cooperation from the Congolese government, inadequate manpower and logistics, the lack of clear political framework in DRC, lack of knowledge and understanding of the cultural and political situation are the factors that hinder the peace process of the UN peacekeeping missions in DRC. However, the study concluded that some solutions to these problems and the way forward for the peacekeeping missions. The study concluded that peacekeeping operations prioritize exerting more efforts towards building a solid-state institution and peacebuilding in DRC. The study concluded that more joint hybrid missions or partnerships between UN peacekeeping operations and African regional organizations as they have a great understanding of the political and cultural situation in DRC and establishment of a clear framework and mandate by the UNSC for the peacekeeping missions are some of the solutions mentioned by the study. In terms of results, the study deduced that despite the Congolese government's lack of collaboration, the report concluded that the UN peacekeeping operations' job is to preserve peace and stability in the DRC by carrying out their authorized objectives of protecting civilians and eliminating armed rebel groups.

Regarding whether the peacekeeping missions in DRC have distinct goals and interests, the researchers concluded that the UN peacekeeping operations do not have a conflict of interest in the situation, but rather a lack of selection and supervision of the peacekeepers deployed. The DRC is rich in natural resources; hence illegal mineral trafficking by foreign entities contributes to the insecurity. The study concluded that the UN peacekeeping's fundamental issue in the DRC is a lack of knowledge and awareness of the country's political and cultural condition, as well as a lack of resources, manpower, a defined framework and mission, and coping with the colonial legacy of underdevelopment, political differences, and poverty. Nonetheless, the study outlined that the UN peacekeeping mission is still a viable tool for maintaining peace and stability in DRC despite not achieving the goal it has hoped for in DRC. Lastly, the study concluded that instability in DRC did not increase because of the establishment of the DRC but rather the instability that existed before the presence of the missions and foreign involvement from Rwanda and Uganda led to the increase in the instability in the DRC.

References

1. Andersen LR, Engedal PE. Blue helmets and grey zones: Do UN multidimensional peace operations work?. DIIS Report; 2013.
2. Agada S. The challenges of United Nations peacekeeping in Africa: Case study of Somalia. Peace Operations Training Institute. 2008 Jan:1-94.
3. "From disarmament to lasting peace: defining the parliamentary role". *Archive.Ipu.Org*. 2004. Accessed December 19, 2021 <http://archive.ipu.org/splz-e/unga04/peacekeeping.pdf>.
4. Sarjoon A, Yusoff MA. The United Nations Peacekeeping Operations and Challenges. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*. 2019 Nov 10;8(3):202-.
5. Bellamy AJ, Paul d. Williams and Stuart Griffin. *Understanding peacekeeping*. 2010.
6. Salaün N. The Challenges Faced by UN Peacekeeping Missions in Africa. *The Strategy Bridge*.
7. Mood R. Force Commanders' Advice to the High-Level Independent Panel on UN Peace Operations.
8. Hervé, Ladsous. "New Challenges and Priorities for UN Peacekeeping." *remarks given at the Brookings Institution* 17 (2014).
9. Halabo TT. Conflicts in the Democratic Republic of Congo: Dynamics, Trends and Challenges for Peace. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*. 2020 Nov 2;17(9):10090-102.
10. Khan Daim M, Edet IH. State Rationales for contributing troops to UN peacekeeping operations. *South Asia Democratic Forum (SADF)*.
11. "UN Denounces Attack On Peacekeepers In DR Congo". *UN News*. 2021. Accessed November 13, 2021 <https://news.un.org/en/story/2021/05/1091682>.
12. Bamidele O. The challenges of peacekeeping in Africa: A revisit. *The Strategic Review for Southern Africa*. 2013;35(2).
13. Kreps SE. Why does peacekeeping succeed or fail? Peacekeeping in the Democratic Republic of Congo and Sierra Leone. *Modern War and the Utility of Force*, edited by Jan Angstrom and Isabelle Duyvesteyn,(New York, Routledge, 2010). 2010.
14. Shirin B. Sexual Exploitation and Abuse by UN Peacekeepers.
15. Findlay T. The use of force in UN peace operations. SIPRI; 2002.
16. Abi-Saab G. *The United Nations Operation in the Congo, 1960-1964*. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press; 1978.
17. Alexander, Novosseloff, A. E. Abdenur, T. Mandrup, and A. Pangburn. "Assessing the Effectiveness of the UN Mission in the DRC (MONUC-MONUSCO)." *Report 3* (2019): 2019.
18. Tarus DK. Effectiveness of United Nation's Missions in Africa: A Comparative Assessment of UNAMSIL, MONUC, and UNAMID. *Army Command and General Staff Coll Fort Leavenworth KS*; 2010 Jun 11.
19. Mutisi M. SADC Interventions in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. *Conflict Trends*. 2016 Jan 1;2016(3):27-35.

20. Diehl PF, Lepage J, editors. Regional conflict management. Rowman & Littlefield Publishers; 2003 Feb 11.
21. G. O, Oguntomisin, *Perspectives on peacekeeping and peace-making in Nigeria's pre-colonial era to the present*. Lagos: Longman Nig. Ltd, (2004): 34.
22. Agwai ML. United Nations Peacekeeping in Africa. *Strategie und Sicherheit*. 2011 Jan 1;2011(1):449-58.
23. Mutisi M. SADC Interventions in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. *Conflict Trends*. 2016 Jan 1;2016(3):27-35.
24. Maiden EK. Transformative Peace in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. *Journal of International Peacekeeping*. 2014 Jun 9;18(1-2):102-22.
25. Swigert JW. Challenges of peacekeeping in Africa. Remarks of the Principal Deputy Assistant Secretary of the Bureau of International Organization Affairs, Department of State, to the Committee on International Relations, US House of Representatives, October. 2004 Aug;8.

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